

IDENTIFICATION OF KNOWLEDGE LEVEL AIMED TO IMPROVE PRODUCTION PROCESSES AND UP-GRADE VALUE ADDED WITHIN COMPANIES

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Abstract

Introduction Importance of process improvement is over two centuries continuous research challenge but in Romania national issues & global approach can rise new problems.

Research problem Nobody evaluated training needs in the field of process improvement. With respect to this problem, we've expressed the **Purpose**: Identification of training needs in automotive field concerning improvements since these are not easy to find if you are not part of the niche and market voice is subsequently hidden.

Methodology/approach Going back to on-site assessment means **face-to-face** interviews, covering the field of automotive producers - parts, components, assemblies and performing National inquiry on almost all Regions and all fields of processes and technologies.

Findings – For training and coaching it isn't enough to ask for Human Resources to find out needs but also Purchasing and other Operational departments. Knowledge management maturity was found not reliable; process improvement projects are not really effective; waste is present and subsequently organization's productivity is not appropriate.

Research limitations/implications – New approach in Romania, time consuming and logistically heavy to perform, complete state-of-the-art level.

Practical implications – Hands-on inquiry, interviews performed on over 2/two Years;

Originality/value – *Complex multidisciplinary assessment, performed on-site; *Holistic approach; *Paradigm change; *Process approach reviewed and changed into Project approach for Lean & QC Story appliances aimed to improve efficiency; agile base was considered as support.

Key words: training needs, processes improvement.

1. Introduction

Survey was conducted over a 2-year period in SMEs and large companies, facing major challenges. Identification of targets in order to improve performance in the area of process improvement was assumed. Risk was that changes in methodological approaches could bring with them changes in mentality and cleavages; the importance of transferring new methods to production of modernized process methodologies is to be noted. A general objective is the development of managerial capacities in Romanian companies, through training, consulting and transfer of skills based on professional assistance in order to improve the competitive position of companies, increase the quality and effectiveness and through them the development of managerial capacities in Romanian companies.

This report presents the results of quantitative research, with qualitative interpretations. The results of the study serve to identify specific training needs of the group considered and to define their improvement actions and adapt the training and assistance activities on line with re-design of production processes.

This will result into identification of differences between the actual level of training of employees and what is desired in terms of performance for employees – this can contribute – if properly managed – to up-grade performance of the company in which they operate.

For the differences identified between expectations and reality, one possible solution is staff training and coaching, especially where there are gaps to fill - identified on the basis of this "gap analysis".

2. Research problem

To carry out a process of training needs identification it is mandatory to gather information to support the decision to choose training programs that (can) solve existing problems. This activity is designed and conducted as a research - collection and analysis of the information received - from key people within Companies: answers provided to questions contained in questionnaires.

The survey is a practical, face-to-face approach to interview decision-makers. We totally avoided internet surveys, to which the responsible factors answer with great reluctance and therefore results in a low participation involvement and lower reliability factor.

Objectives raised from problem research of the survey-based research:

1. Identify actual situation of training in a particular – automotive – field: what employees already know; have they necessary knowledge in order to carry out activities? Is it correlated with the HR training requirements for achieving operational objectives?
2. Identifying need for training - what employees need to know in order to improve their performance - (Erick Jones, 2014, pag. 627) "knowledge management"; perception also covers the maturity level of the QMS;
3. Identify the perception of key people within the company on operational issues;
4. Identify the types of training that will help improve performance;
5. Identify ways to test the growth of knowledge and skills or adapted techniques.

3. Methodology including sampling/population

The sampled **population** included employees with managerial missions and responsibilities in production management field, on process improvement projects and process engineering.

Methods & techniques included the appropriate resources planning, the approach, the methodology and subsequent tools

The research was carried out through both **organizational and functional analysis**, as the problems considered to be important were those of performance in the field of process improvement. The organizational analysis consists of organization as a whole diagnosis in order to find out malfunctions. Elements such as strategic axes, key indicators and organizational culture have been taken into account.

Prospective field visits were made, during which we met leading people from general management, human resources, production or quality. They provided useful information for identifying specific training level, training needs and the will of transfer of new knowledge, skills and attitudes. A purpose was to research the company's potential management's interest in a training and assistance program proposed by an international team, as well as to identify the company's own, specific training and assistance needs.

The amount of data needed to carry out diagnosis were **obtained by interviews**. Obtained information & data, creates-on a degree of correlation between the operational objectives of marketing, design, production, quality and human resources departments. This correlation had to draw a pattern concerning the level of performance and the overall profile of employees with managerial duties in management and production improvement, using next formats:

- Identification sheets of potential customer requirements and expectations;

- Answer grid for "customer requirements and expectations identification sheet";
- Visit report documenting company key person attendance list answering to inquiry

A questionnaire "Customer Requirements and Expectations Identification Sheet" was conducted – administered directly by the Coordinator/first author and operated, discussed and completed. The questionnaire contains a number of questions, 80% being open **questions** - and 20% being closed **questions** – in order to facilitate the dialogue with deciders.

In terms of Companies, **the sample** was selected between Automotive Organizations. Use of questionnaires attached to the customer's requirements and expectations identification sheets were answered **by a number >80 companies***, all from manufacturing domain. After the survey, many companies were interested in applying into training/coaching projects.

Interviews were conducted on **more than 120* persons** – a representative sample.

(*) NOTE: 80 Companies represents 25% of the Automotive Companies out of a total between 360-380: statistically reliable with a 95 % indices of confidence, and a +/- 3% error margins.

4. Findings

4.1 Data analysis and interpretation

Data gathered have been reported into graphs and figures in such a way that interpretation could become as reliable as possible. **Pie chart** graphs prevailed, especially where the answers had to show the comparative factorial aspects. Comments were not neglected: verbatims provided by interviewees were included in(to) the analysis; we've included comments where answers didn't prove to be reliable.

It should be pointed out that certain comments are not available in case of online surveys, hence the quality of this study, which is **pushed** towards confession and, possibly, factual, based on objective indicators or evidence – is not quite possible for online surveys.

4.2 Efficiency of production flows - DMAIC re-engineering needs

The scope of the firms was the manufacturing industry mainly automotive industry and the level of interest of companies in acquiring DMAIC techniques, process improvement projects and/or reducing non-quality costs was focused. It was explained to the companies participating in the questionnaire that participation in projects aimed at improving **competences** of participants, target being defined: managers, process engineers, technicians. 14 firms of those surveyed did not participate in fulfillment of the questionnaire but accepted open discussions and authors recorded their requirements and expectations; we can expect that in case of online inquiries these people could just deny answer. Following the interview, the following analyses were found for each situation:

Question 1.: Have you defined within your organization the function responsible for improving processes or redesigning existing processes? - see Figure 1.

For 76.5% of the companies surveyed, the appointment of a person responsible for process improvement RIP-Responsible for Process Improvement is a priority but unpractically defined and not factual implemented. Directors Boards have made them aware of this way of increasing market competitiveness and are looking to implement improvement projects. Additionally, it appeared in nomenclatures on trades approaches of the type Responsible improvement processes. They are not currently missioned (no link to requirements of Lean Manufacturing or LSS) as they try to set principles and objectives for trainings. Companies proved to have some doubts about the proper understanding of such a Responsible role.

Figure 1. Definition of people responsible for process redesign

Question 2: Do you encounter difficulties in redesigning appropriate process flows ? - see Figure 2.

At (re)designing production flows after a period of activity it was found that in some respects the flows do not correspond to planned expectations. According to the firms surveyed, most of them had difficulties. In this situation, the survey responses were quite reliable. The appearance was considered gratifying, because the respondents were aware of some efforts but knew that the efforts were either not successful or were partially winning and would have liked to consider factual/effective methods of resolution. Often the lack of vision of FLM - front line managers (Ortiz, 2016) has worked starting since the basics - production cell / work cell. It has been noted that *work cell* is not considered relevant (did not attempted goals).

Figure 2. The level of difficulties encountered in redesigning process flows.

Question 3: Difficulties encountered relate to - see Figure 3, a), b), c), d):

a) Planning of development stages, taking into account customer requirements?

The first step in re-designing some production flows is the Planning of the Development of a Process. This planning is often difficult, say over 50% of managers surveyed. Although it seems quite a lot, the imbalance is much more obvious if you take into account the notes contained in the YES answer, it *is difficult* leading the weight towards >70%.

b) The flow design and/or redesign?

Designing and redesigning a stream must be a well-thought-out step involving risks. A significant 37.5 percent of the firms surveyed say they have encountered no problems so far. This may be due to the fact that they have benefice from Head Office consulting or advice from specialized teams since multinationals already have supported them with redesigned plans.

c) Framing in the final deadlines / planning stages?

Planning to perform a redesigned process should not affect the fixed delivery deadlines. The redesigned process needs to be well planned and its implementation to fall within deadlines and not into bottlenecks. RIB must assess all risks that may occur during the process of redesigning and implementing new process, establishing Critical Path within the target time. Of the firms surveyed >50 experienced difficulties, representing >80%.

If we question that re-planning is done from the office in order to save time but applied in the field, it becomes quite clear that there are more 20% of over scheduling cases due to **office work without process knowledge** but is possible % to be even worst due to specific conditions (please follow the trace into the next stage, related to human factor and working in teams). Many aspects prove that flow designer doesn't know or practically cannot take into account processes related risks.

d) Ensuring functioning and communication in multidisciplinary teams?

The RIP has to take into account both objective factors - facilities (equipment, locations, logistic flow) and subjective factors - people (motivation, lack of competence) at the level required within interdisciplinary teams – or, finally the absence of Leadership. Problems related to human factors, communication problems, facilitation and negotiation problems or conflicts of interest are usually felt within the teams designated to carry out a project. This can be improved only if members are meeting each other and work on project or share with other teams designated for various projects. 82.8% of companies experience this kind of problem.

Figure 3.

- a) – Share of difficulties in the planning of development stages
- b) – Share of difficulties in designing and redesigning the flow
- c) – Share of difficulties in relation to compliance with planned deadlines
- d) – Share of difficulties in relation to the functioning of interdisciplinary teams

Question 4. Feasibility of producing under conditions of synchronous streams? - see Figure 4

In this approach in the questionnaire there are actually caught two main aspects: the first is the **feasibility of the project aimed to improve the flow**, which implies the existence of all resources for the planned risks, the second is the analysis of the indicators before the **redesign of the flow**. From the point of view of implementation, resources are the basis, but from the point of view of synchronization there are still not all the prerequisites, therefore a sufficiently crystal-clear YES is possible in < 15% of cases. When designing a synchronous flow, it is necessary to take into account that process capacity, balance and capability must be obtained on all sub-flows. To design a synchronous flow capable of meeting the customer's requirement for a T/T - takt time, each sub-flow requires a pre-defined C/T – cycle time, to lead to a correct capacitive response.

Figure 4. Share of difficulties in assuming the feasibility of synchronous flows

Question 5 Effective use of resources allocated to re-planning? - see Figure 5

Resources are in any project planning a huge problem (mainly in re-planning). Resources within a re-planning action must be adequate and based on records of resources previously used in planning. Before submitting any data and figures, the basis is the analysis of what was right and/or what was wrong with the previous planning: see TGG & TGW - things gone good/wrong. When we refer to resources we understand: time resources, allocated budgets, material resources: equipment may already exist, only site configuration is to be changed, human resources - here you can list both people involved in dismantling-reassembly, and personnel for logistics – transport or handling. Reasons for the above results are obvious (Klaus Altendorfer, 2014) and are confirmed by the results of the survey and the reasons why 92.1% of the companies surveyed say they had problems.

Figure 5. Share of difficulties in the use of resources allocated (re)planning

Question 6 Competence of staff involved in (re)planning? - see Figure 6

Staff involved in re-planning are often at the beginning of the road (if not for other reasons, at least because these aspects are not displayed in theory at the level of university degree). Many of the RIP are self-taught, with the necessary costs of training considered quite substantial. Such a RIP that has

not worked with KPIs – key process indicators: L/T – lead time, C/T, T/T, Cmk – machine capability, Cpk – process capability, Ppk – process performance, Cgk measuring equipment capability, with machine usage times, operating times, with effectiveness analysis – OEE – overall equipment effectiveness, will not understand their involvement into reaching appropriate targets.

Processes such as those that carry out production VA - value added, but also support processes: quality, logistics, maintenance, purchases, human resources, are in direct re-planning involvement. Out of the firms surveyed, 36 said they had encountered problems in terms of staff competence ≈50%.

Figure 6. Share of difficulties in the competence of involved staff in case of (re)planning

Question 7: Do you use Risk Analysis in flow planning/development? - see Figure 7

Risk analyses in flow planning/development are essential preventive activities for smooth running of processes. This analysis is not cost-effective when the series are not very large. Moving over this stage is traditionally done so positive responses were often preceded by empirically fire fighter style actions that proved their inefficiency. As is also apparent from the questionnaire, there are companies that apply risk analyses in flow re-planning. Here the sample is not representative at national level since companies in the automotive area have been approached into this survey, those practicing PFMEA – process risk analyses. They acknowledged that, to a large extent, the results are formal and that they want to improve their performance.

Figure 7. Call for risk analyses on flow schedules

5. Survey conclusions

It was found that of the total of enterprises surveyed a significant percentage would like to include in the course(s) scopes concerning teamwork skills (soft skills). This aspect is much more pronounced when it comes to approach team development of the couple product/process, which is a team built-up of staff from several departments and who do not carry out all their daily work together.

With regard to the willingness to engage in a training programme for the development of skills relating to the use of tools that reduce product release times or the number of non-conformities at the design stage, the results indicate favourable attitudes of the majority of companies.

Participants - some of - wish only to develop skills related to understanding and using their Risk Analyses, others would like to develop working skills in multidisciplinary teams and techniques for product development. There are also enterprises that have chosen both aspects: product development, re-planning production processes, but nominating different people, depending on their role within the organization. Thus, in most enterprises, employees are willing to participate for a period of 3 to 10 days in the training program. For the courses with a duration of 10 days, however, it is necessary to divide into 2 sessions of 5 days each, and between them a period of coaching is required to be intercalated.

Another important aspect is that of adapting the training programme to the specific requirements of clients - Companies that have been established as beneficiaries - with regard to the presentation of examples related to their own products and processes, and in some cases also the use of own documents of the organisation to be understood equally by all participants.

6. Contributions of integrated trainings & coaching

In this survey, authors are recommending as a matter of priority the following:

- Design of learning activities should be guided by the specific principles of adult training, including strategy of: teaching – learning through games and plays, assessment, coaching.
- Design of practical guides (Patel, 2016) approaches for an effective implementation of Lean/Agile.
- Inclusion of chapters that address different aspects of teamwork – from the definition of concept to its exemplification through role-playing or exercise.
- Performing training activities in such a way as to achieve a homogenization of the knowledge of all participants, without letting those who possess more knowledge get bored.
- Lecturers take into account that the vast majority of people assessed upon entry into the training program have a level of skills. By managing the initial test results, the actual level can be better observed. It is the starting point in the development of skills.
- The use of AGILE methods (Rothman, 2016) taken from the automotive field, not (of) those out of the IT field, here is imposed QC Story, used by two major OEM companies, a methodology that provides theoretical knowledge of the type lean manufacturing for managers of the level Heads of Teams, representing the recruitment base of the support staff for projects.

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